

On the thermal management of torpedo ladle car logistics at Tata Steel in IJmuiden

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Abstract

Torpedo ladle cars at Tata Steel in IJmuiden, Netherlands are filled with hot metal based on the first-in-first-out principle, which appears to be non-optimal. Due to higher hot metal temperatures, increased volumes of hot metal per unit of time and insulation of torpedo linings, the refractory wear rate has gone up. This has led to a significant increase of the refractory maintenance costs. Therefore a thermal-logistics plant model was developed as part of a future overall logistics model to allow for optimal management of torpedo cars. The thermal model is based on a detailed thermal finite-element method (FEM) model, which in turn is based on thermocouple measurements of a torpedo refractory lining. The thermal-logistics model has been implemented in the torpedo management systems of the blast furnaces at Tata Steel in IJmuiden and is found to accurately predict the hot metal temperature upon arrival in the steel plant.

1. Introduction

Blast furnace hot metal is commonly transported to the steel plant by a torpedo ladle car. The lining of a torpedo ladle mainly consists of a thick wear lining, a safety lining and a thin insulation lining against the steel shell. It is important to minimize heat losses of the hot metal as much as possible, as this will have a positive impact on the downstream processing to liquid steel in the basic oxygen steel (BOS) plant.

Fig. 1 One of the torpedo ladle cars of Tata Steel in IJmuiden.

The torpedo cars used at Tata Steel in IJmuiden roughly contain 350 to 380 tonnes of liquid iron (hot metal). The transport time from the blast furnace to the BOS plant including casting for further processing, is 4 hours on average. After casting its contents into a hot metal ladle, the torpedo ladle

remains empty for approximately 6 hours on average. Currently, torpedo ladle cars at Tata Steel IJmuiden are filled with hot metal based on the first-in-first-out principle, which appears to be non-optimal. Due to higher hot metal temperatures, increased volumes of hot metal per unit of time and insulation of torpedo linings, the refractory wear rate has gone up. This has led to an increase of the refractory maintenance costs by 30%. The aim is therefore to develop a thermal-logistics plant model as part of an overall logistics model to allow for optimal management of the torpedo ladle car fleet of Tata Steel in IJmuiden. Such a thermal model predicts the refractory temperature of every torpedo ladle car in service at any moment, and it predicts the hot metal temperature of every filled torpedo ladle at any moment. Ideally, the model uses actual information on refractory wear, hot metal volume, hot metal temperature, et cetera.

Fig. 2 Schematic overview of the torpedo ladle car logistics.

The thermal-logistics model that was developed for this purpose, is based on a detailed thermal FEM model, which in turn is validated by thermocouple measurements. This FEM model was used to simulate “all” possible process scenarios (95 %) which occur for the torpedo ladles in IJmuiden. Subsequently, a set of three easy-to-program empirical equations was defined and fit to the FEM simulation results, resulting in a relatively simple

thermal-logistics model. This model is currently implemented in the torpedo management systems of the blast furnaces at Tata Steel in IJmuiden. As said, in the near future this thermal model will be used as part of an overall logistics model including wear models and economics models to optimize torpedo logistics with respect to their value-in-use, including reducing refractory maintenance and production costs.

2. Thermocouple measurements

As with every model, the simulation results are as good as the model input. This input includes material properties, process data and (thermal) boundary conditions. In order to establish accurate thermal boundary conditions such as ambient temperature conditions and heat transfer coefficients, a thermocouple measurement campaign was set up. During this campaign, a torpedo ladle was mounted with 30 thermocouples and monitored for nearly 8 months.

Fig. 3 Measured temperatures at various locations in the refractory lining during the first two weeks of the measurement campaign.

Fig. 3 shows part of the results of the first two weeks of the thermocouple measurement campaign, including the heat up. It can be seen that some thermocouples measure a temperature plateau at 100 °C which indicates the evaporation of water from the refractory lining.

3. Computational approach

3.1 Finite-element model

The torpedo ladle was modelled in full 3d using the finite-element method (FEM) in ANSYS®.¹⁾ The model includes surface-to-surface radiation and heat transfer to the ambient by radiation and by convection based on empirical natural convection relations²⁾ and on computational fluid dynamics (CFD) calculations from previous research at Tata Steel R&D. The hot metal is modelled as an ‘effective

solid’ with a high thermal conductivity to mimic the convective flow of the hot metal bath. This bath can be ‘switched on and off’ to simulate a full or empty torpedo ladle, respectively. The refractory materials properties are obtained by materials characterization measurements at our labs. Below in **Fig. 4** open views of the FEM model are shown including the thermal profile when the torpedo ladle is filled with hot metal.

Fig. 4 FEM model showing the element mesh (top, $\frac{3}{4}$ view) and a thermal profile (°C) when the torpedo ladle is filled (bottom, $\frac{1}{2}$ view).

The hot metal effective thermal conductivity and the heat transfer coefficient of the hot metal to the refractory lining are derived from the thermocouple measurements in the refractory lining, see **Sec. 2** above. These measurements are also used to validate the convective heat transfer from the torpedo ladle shell to the ambient.

Fig. 5 Measured temperatures (diamonds) and calculated temperatures using the FEM model

(lines) of the torpedo ladle lining during preheat and the first 4 cycles.

In Fig. 5 it can be seen that the agreement between the measurements and the FEM simulation results is excellent. The only exception is the measured temperature plateau at 100 °C during heating up due to the evaporation of water. This effect has not been included in the FEM model, which seems to be justified as it appears to diminish during the remainder of the preheat and even more during the first hot metal transport cycle. The process scenarios simulated with the FEM model comprise 95 % of all scenarios that occurred in the last year regarding full and empty times, casting and tapping times, hot metal temperature, hot metal volume, and wear of the refractory lining. This sets the application limits of the thermal-logistics model and provides the temperature data for detailing the thermal-logistics model.

3.2 Thermal-logistics model

The thermal-logistics model consists of three empirical equations. One equation describes the hot metal temperature, T_m , and two equations describe the (average) refractory temperature: one when the torpedo ladle is filled with hot metal, $T_{r,f}$, and one when it is empty, $T_{r,e}$:

$$T_m = T_{m,BF} - \frac{\alpha_1 \cdot (T_{m,BF} - T_{r,BF})^{\tau_1}}{D^{\delta_1} \cdot M^{\mu_1}} \cdot Z_f^{\xi_1} - \frac{\beta_1}{M^{\eta_1}} \cdot Z_f^{\xi_1}$$

$$T_{r,f} = T_{r,BF} + \frac{\alpha_2 \cdot (T_{m,BF} - T_{r,BF})^{\tau_2} \cdot M^{\mu_2}}{D_r^{\delta_2}} \cdot Z_f^{\xi_2} - \frac{\beta_2}{D^{\eta_2}} \cdot Z_f^{\xi_2}$$

$$T_{r,e} = T_0 + (T_{r,BOS} - T_0) \times \exp \left[-\frac{\alpha_3 \cdot (T_{r,BOS} - T_0)^{\tau_3}}{D^{\delta_3}} \cdot Z_e^{\xi_3} \right] \quad (1)$$

In the set of Equations (1), T denotes temperature (T_0 is the ambient temperature), D is the average thickness of the refractory wear lining, M is the amount of hot metal in the torpedo ladle, and Z is the time. The labels m and r refer to ‘hot metal’ and ‘refractory’, respectively; f and e stand for ‘full’ and ‘empty’; BF and BOS indicate ‘at the blast furnace’ and ‘at the BOS plant’. The Greek symbols are the model parameters, their values being determined from fitting to the FEM model simulation results. Thus, T_m is the hot metal temperature as a function of

full time Z_f (i.e., the transport time to the BOS plant), $T_{r,f}$ is the averaged refractory wear lining temperature during that same time, and $T_{r,e}$ is the refractory temperature during transport of the empty torpedo back to the blast furnace (empty time Z_e). Similarly, $T_{m,BF}$ is the temperature of the hot metal being tapped in the torpedo ladle at the blast furnace and $T_{r,BOS}$ is the refractory temperature after emptying the torpedo at the BOS plant. In Fig. 6 below a typical curve fit of the thermal-logistics model defined by the set of Equations (1) to the FEM simulation results is shown. Clearly, the curve fit is very good.

Fig. 6 Thermal-logistics model fit (lines) to the FEM simulation results (symbols). Top: hot metal temperature, T_m ; bottom: average refractory temperature, T_r .

4 Implementation of the thermal-logistics model

The thermal-logistics model was successfully implemented in the blast furnace torpedo ladle car management system. In order to monitor its performance, hot metal temperature measurements were done at the BOS plant during emptying of the torpedo ladles at the BOS plant. The results are shown below in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Thermal-logistics model prediction of the

hot metal temperatures (solid lines) and average refractory temperatures (broken lines) versus hot metal temperature measurements (squares) of two torpedo ladle cars.

From **Fig. 7** it is evident that the plant model gives an accurate prediction of the hot metal temperature, allowing for further optimization of the torpedo car logistics.

5 Conclusions

In order to optimize the thermal management of the torpedo ladle car fleet at Tata Steel in IJmuiden, Netherlands, a comprehensive thermal-logistics model was developed and implemented. This model is based on FEM simulation results, the FEM model in turn is based on thermocouple measurements.

(1) The FEM model accurately describes the temperatures in the refractory lining of the torpedo ladle.

(2) The set of three Equations defining the thermal-logistics model fits very well to the FEM simulation results.

(3) The implemented thermal-logistics model accurately predicts the hot metal temperature upon casting at the BOS plant.

(4) The thermal management of the entire torpedo ladle car fleet of Tata Steel in IJmuiden is significantly enhanced by the thermal-logistics model.

References

- 1) ANSYS® Mechanical Enterprise, Release 18.0.
- 2) VDI-Gesellschaft Verfahrenstechnik und Chemieingenieurwesen ed.: VDI Heat Atlas, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, 2010.

